

SIR PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY
MEMORIAL LECTURE *

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I consider it a great privilege to be invited to deliver the Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture this year, and my best thanks are due to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for this honour.

Five years have rolled away since the great savant left this world, full of years and honours. To many of you of the younger generation to-day, he is perhaps only a slowly fading memory, but to those of us who had the privilege of intimate association with him in the early formative years of our lives, he would never cease to be our *Guru* and preceptor, for, in our innermost thoughts and actions even now, particularly when we are in doubts or difficulties, our minds turn unconsciously to him, thinking of how our Professor would have reacted to such and such situations in life, and in many an emergency we still seek light and guidance from him.

It was in July 1906, more than 43 years ago, that I had the first opportunity of coming into contact with Professor P. C. Ray, sitting at his feet as one of his pupils in the third year B.Sc. classes of the Presidency College, Calcutta, under the old regulations of the Calcutta University. To us, freshmen, in those early days of our career, everything in the College seemed to be awe-inspiring: from the imposing buildings, the wide staircases and corridors, the large laboratories in the innermost recesses of which some wizard, we were told, was trying to change copper into gold, or another trying to prove that plants had the same feelings and impulses of pleasure and pain, of joy and sorrow, and responded to stimuli in the same way as animals, to the elegant lecture theatres, and libraries, and, last but not the least, the dignified Professors who seemed to walk at a great height and distance from us. But, in a short time I was aware of a feeling—and this was perhaps the experience of many of my fellow-students—that there was at least one of them who had come closer and established a sort of personal contact with me, and this was no other than the Professor of Chemistry. This was the unique characteristic of Professor P.C. Ray—he never kept his students at a distance, but admitted them very soon into the intimacy of his thoughts and even of friendship. His lectures were never laboured, nor did he seek to make them erudite, but they were always punctuated with good experimental demonstrations, and his simple talk was full of homilies and illustrations from life, intended to drive home to us, beginners, the elementary laws of chemistry—the laws of chemical combination, decomposition, etc. On some days, while discussing a topic in chemistry, he would suddenly make a digression to some of the social evils which were rampant in our society—they were probably rankling in his mind all the time, he having come across reports of a particu-

* Delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on August 2, 1949 at Calcutta.

larly bad case in the morning papers that day—the evils of the caste system, of untouchability, of early marriages of immature youths and maidens, of systems of extorting dowries from the poor parents of girls, and so on. He would warm up while speaking on what he called blots on our society and make apt quotations often full of satire, bearing on these problems from the poems of Tagore and other Bengali writers of the day. Our lecture in chemistry on that day would end with a sermon preached with eloquence, grace and humour for the benefit of his intimate circle of students, on whom, however, it never failed to create a deep and abiding impression. This was the essence of his philosophy as a teacher : He did not consider himself bound by the four walls of chemistry but like all true Gurus, he regarded his pupils as his children and his most intimate friends, entitled to share not merely his knowledge of the science of chemistry but his innermost thoughts and feelings on the burning problems of life as well. On other days again, he would be full of enthusiasm on a subject of research, which was immediately engaging his attention : it did not form a part of our course or curriculum, but syllabuses or curricula did not trouble him, nor deter him from unfolding before our enraptured gaze some of the secret methods of his researches. One such day I vividly remember : the rolls of the students attending the lecture had just been called as usual, by his assistant, when Professor Ray stepped into the class and shook before our eyes a small bottle containing what seemed to be some pale yellow crystals. With his inimitable jump of delight, he drew our attention to what he said was a new substance which he had been seeking for sometime, and which he had just then succeeded in preparing. He called it Silver-Mercuroso-Mercuric-Nitrate, explaining to us the method of its preparation and immediately proceeding to demonstrate the presence in the salt of the different silver, mercurous, mercuric and nitrate ions. These were some of the special features of Sir Prafulla's lectures to his junior classes. He drew the hearts of the boys out to him, which was undoubtedly the reason why they never found a moment of their hour with him dull or uninteresting.

As I look back upon those days of our studies at the Presidency College, Calcutta, with Dr. Jagadish Bose as the presiding genius of the Physics Department and Dr. Prafulla Ray, the presiding genius in Chemistry, memories of the past rush into my mind and I have a feeling—the present generation of students will, I hope, forgive me for cherishing this pride of contemporary times, a feeling that we had the good fortune of studying in that great Institution when it was at the pinnacle of its fame and glory. It was during our post-graduate studies, however, from 1908 to 1910 that we were thrown into the most intimate contact with our Professor. We were privileged to watch at close quarters the research experiments carried out by him and his assistants, and some of us were even permitted, particularly during holidays, to assist him in these researches. It was at this time that some of us were in the habit of visiting him occasionally in the evenings. Many were the delightful hours which we spent with him in conversations of absorbing interest in his austere little bedroom in the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works office at 91, Upper Circular Road, Calcutta, where he resided in those days. On these occasions he would talk without reserve and tell us the fascinating story of his rich experiences in life, of his hopes and

fears, his joys and sorrows, of the numerous problems—educational and social, political and industrial—facing the people, and his high hopes about solving them with the help of his young students, whom he considered to be the spearhead of all progress in the country. The memory of those days, of the joyous aspirations and bright hopes raised in our young minds, can never be effaced or dimmed.

I do not wish to speak in detail on the various topics of researches in which Professor Ray had been engaged during his long career as a Professor of Chemistry. His researches on nitrites, particularly those of mercury, are now common knowledge and form the subject of text-books in chemistry. These researches covered roughly the period of two decades from 1892 to 1912. Many were the publications which found their way during this period from the chemical laboratories of the Presidency College to the Scientific journals of Europe and attracted the notice of such well known workers as Rainsay, Roscoe, Divers, Velej and others. From the elusive and unstable ammonium nitrite, which Professor Ray first prepared in the pure state, subliming the crystals in a vacuum and showing that the vapour had normal density, it was but the next step for him to proceed to prepare and study the stabilities of the alkyl ammonium nitrites, which were obtained by the double decomposition of alkyl amine hydrochlorides and silver nitrite in cold aqueous solution. It is very pleasant to recall the fact that my first apprenticeship at research under Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray began in 1910 on the preparation and thermal decomposition in a Sprengel vacuum of tetramethyl ammonium nitrite and tetramethyl ammonium hyponitrite. I would like to digress a little at this point from the main theme of this lecture and relate to you an incident of our early experience in the preparation of the starting material for this research—an incident which might almost have ended in a disaster. Tetramethyl ammonium nitrite required the preparation in the first instance of tetramethyl ammonium iodide, for which the only known method was the old Hofmann reaction between methyl iodide and liquor ammonia by heating under pressure in sealed tubes at steam temperatures. Our first experiment was entirely successful, although we were unaware of it, and, on opening the tubes, crystals were found to have separated from the cold liquid, shining like jewels. According to literature, however, these crystals were supposed to be mainly those of ammonium iodide and hence to be neglected, the tetramethyl ammonium salt being obtained only from the filtered liquid after boiling with potash to liberate the free trimethyl, dimethyl and methyl amines from their combinations with hydriodic acid, and then concentrating the liquid. I need hardly say that this procedure never yielded the material, and our repeated failures to obtain the desired compound led one day to a disastrous explosion in the laboratory, the loud report of which was heard throughout the building; the water-bath in which the sealed tubes were being heated had run dry while we were attending a lecture, and this led to the shattering explosion. The unfortunate accident drew on our heads the wrath and censure of the whole of the laboratory staff, of whom the chief and the most feared but respected member was the late Prof. Chandrabhushan Bhaduri. Fortunately for us this accident led eventually to the detection of our error in rejecting as ammonium iodide what was really slightly impure tetramethyl ammonium iodide which was later obtained pure after one or two

crystallisations from water. The interaction of this iodide with silver nitrite and silver hyponitrite in warm aqueous solutions gave the desired quaternary ammonium nitrite and hyponitrite.

It is with feelings of deep gratitude that I recall the great encouragement and help which I received from the Professor in my first attempt at independent research which was also on the subject of nitrites, viz., the interaction of hydrazine salts with nitrites, in which I had the valued collaboration of my late lamented friend, Dr. H. K. Sen. It may be of interest to my present audience to know that one of the methods for estimation of nitrites, which was very dear to our Professor, involved the use of the Crum Nitrometer, which used to be a most potent weapon in his hands in the prosecution of these researches. The nitrometer consisted of a graduated tube open at one end and with a stop-cock and a cup at the other end. This was filled with mercury and inverted in a trough of mercury, with the cup at the top. The solution of the nitrite (definite volume) was put into the cup and gradually introduced by opening the stop-cock carefully and finally washing it in with distilled water. A few drops of strong sulphuric acid were introduced from the bottom of the tube under the mercury trough when NO was given off which collected at the top of the nitrometer and its volume read off and corrected to N.T.P. It gave the most accurate results in our estimations of nitrites and was very frequently used by Professor Ray in his researches. The results of our work were published in the *Zeitschrift für anorganische Chemie* of April, 1911, and was reviewed in the Annual Reports on the Progress of Chemistry of that year. In August 1911 I sailed for England for studies in research in Organic Chemistry in the laboratories of the Imperial College—Royal College of Science, London, and the following summer (June, 1912) Professor Ray came to London as a delegate from the Calcutta University to the Empire Universities Conference, held in London that year. I might mention here an incident which illustrates better than anything else the sort of relationship which Professor Ray had with his pupils. I had no definite information about the date when Professor Ray was expected to arrive in London, or about the place where he was going to stay, but one day, early in June, as I was working in the morning in the laboratory, the laboratory-boy came to me with a card which I found to be that of Prof. P. C. Ray, saying that the gentleman was waiting outside. Professor Ray had ridden straight from the Victoria station to the Imperial College, knowing as if by instinct where he would get immediate help and relief, and he asked, nay, ordered me to take him straight to my lodgings ! I mention this incident only to show the great love and trust which existed between Sir P. C. Ray and his pupils—a trust, which is so rare to find now-a-days. Then began a period of intimacy as between a *guru* and a *shishya*, when I had the privilege of acting as his friend and guide, escorting him to the various places which he wanted to visit and to the meetings which he had to attend, of acting as his amanuensis, and drafting his various letters and even nursing him at times when he became indisposed. I believe he addressed two Thursday evening meetings of the London Chemical Society on the subject of his researches on the "amine nitrites" which were specially attended by Professors Veley and Ramsay ; the latter give him an ovation at the end of his discourse, saying that Dr. Ray had almost singlehanded kept the torch of Science burning in that ancient land which was carried with acclamation by all the members

present. Our summer of 1912 in London was a memorable one, full of the happiest memories. Not only were there a number of distinguished personages from India, like Gokhale and others, whom we had opportunities of meeting quite often, but there was also our beloved poet Rabindranath Tagore, who came with his son and daughter-in-law and took up his residence in Alfred Place in South Kensington, very close to our club at 21, Cromwell Road. There was hardly a day without lectures, evening soirees, meetings and at-homes of some kind or other, and we the students threw ourselves wholeheartedly into the general excitement of the festivities to the detriment, perhaps, of our real work and studies.

It was my proud privilege to step into the shoes of Prof. P. C. Ray at the Presidency College, Calcutta on my return from England, when at the beginning of November, 1916, Professor Ray took a year's leave, preparatory to retirement, and joined the College of Science as the Palit Professor of Chemistry at the earnest request of the then Vice-Chancellor, the late Sir Asutosh Mookerjee. In those early days of severance of his connection with the Presidency College, Professor Ray's heart still remained in his old College, and on many an occasion, he would pay surprise visits to my laboratory and ask to be allowed to take up a part of my hour with the students to address them.

The *Magnum Opus* of Sir P. C. Ray's work may perhaps be considered to be the history of Hindu Chemistry on which he laboured for years with the help of several Sanskrit Pandits of Calcutta. It was published in two volumes, volume the first in 1902 and volume the second in 1908. A good portion of Volume II is taken up by a contribution on the positive sciences of the Ancient Hindus from the pen of the late Sir Brajendranath Seal who was then the Principal of the Victoria College, Cooch-Bihar, and who later went to Mysore at the invitation of the Maharaja to take up the post of the first Vice-Chancellor of the University of Mysore. The work has now become classical and attracted the attention of chemists all over the world. It is, I believe out of print and it is in the fitness of things that the Indian Chemical Society now is making an endeavour to publish a revised and enlarged edition of the book with a grant from the Central Government.

It is not my task to-day to make a comprehensive survey of the manifold activities of Professor Ray in the various fields of educational, scientific, literary and social work, and it will be difficult, even if I had the abilities for it to do so in the course of this lecture. I would, however, fail in my duty if I omitted to mention the fact that Professor Ray, though essentially a chemist, was no narrow specialist; he had wide sympathies and a rich and receptive mind full of intelligent appreciation of the beauties of art, literature and history, and he often used to take his students, particularly his research assistants and other advanced pupils to task for their neglect and ignorance of the humanities. In 1910 Professor Ray was elected President for the annual meeting of the Bangiya Sahitya Parishad, which was to be held at Rajshahi in Bengal, and I remember the enthusiasm with which he threw himself into the work of composing his Presidential Address, which created a deep impression on the literary circles in Bengal and received their homage and admiration. He has since written on many subjects, in numerous journals and magazines, has spoken from many platforms, and in times of emergency and crisis in the country has always been in the forefront in coming to the

rescue of his distressed fellow-beings. His "Impressions of a Bengalee Chemist", written in two volumes towards the end of his life, would bear testimony to his wide interests in life and his multifarious activities.

No estimate of the value of his contributions to the advancement of his countrymen would be complete which did not take note of his pioneering labours in the foundations of chemical industries in this country. The Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works are deservedly considered to be his direct offspring, but there are numerous others which are flourishing to-day, which his inspiring example and genius and encouragement helped in bringing into existence. He was never tired of exhorting his countrymen to take to industries and commerce and not hanker for jobs under Government, and he always held before the youths of the country the examples of men the world over who, through tireless industry and self-confidence, rose from small beginnings to the positions of industrial magnates, and who gave, as he did himself, their large earnings for philanthropic objects for the benefit of humanity.

It would be no exaggeration to state that the ambition to utilise scientific knowledge for the removal of the industrial backwardness and the consequent degrading poverty of the country was first kindled in many of us when we heard from his own lips the wonderful story of the growth of the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works from a small beginning in the nineties of the last century, when he and a few friends scaped together about a thousand rupees out of their small savings for starting this concern, to its present stature of perhaps the premier chemical and pharmaceutical concern in India.

APPLICATION OF THE ELECTRIC CURRENT TO THE MANUFACTURE OF ORGANIC CHEMICALS

It would therefore be only appropriate, I believe, if I spoke to-day on one of these scientific industrial problems which I have been engaged in investigating lately, viz., the application of the electric current to the manufacture of certain organic chemicals of industrial importance—a subject of immense significance in the development of several basic industries of this country. Electricity enters to-day into the production of a large variety of basic materials, such as metals, alloys, chemicals and fertilisers, abrasives, etc. Many of these serve as raw materials for other industries. In some of these, the use of electricity is indispensable as in the production of aluminium, sodium, magnesium, calcium carbide, fused alumina, etc., while in others it is preferred to the chemical processes, as it leads to purer products and are often more economical. Organic products cannot of course compare in bulk and value with the inorganic products of electrochemical industries, but many of these find important uses as dye-intermediates, photographic developers and drugs. It is all the more regrettable therefore, that the subject of manufacture of organic compounds by electrolytic methods has not been given the prominence which it undoubtedly deserves. This is not because electrolytic methods have not been employed in organic industries—in fact, numerous applications have occurred—but, as Thatcher, one of the pioneers of technical electrochemistry in U. S. A., has said "it will probably be difficult, if not impossible, to cite another branch of applied science in which such extreme reticence has been maintained." The typical reactions of organic chemistry like reduction, oxidation and substitution may often be

3. *o*-Nitroanisole,4. *o*-Nitrochlorobenzene,

6. 2-Nitro-4-chloroanisole,

[where R' = OMe or OEt]

I. Nitrobenzene

The electro-reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline media has been studied by numerous workers. Some of the more important of these only are cited here. Straub was one of the first to study the electro-reduction of nitrobenzene and took out a patent on this process (D. R. P. 79731 of 1891) He carried out the reduction in alcoholic caustic potash and claimed to have obtained hydrazo-benzene in a yield of 85%. Wulfing (D. R. P. 110234 of 1898) claimed an improvement by substituting sodium acetate for the caustic alkali, which led to lesser tar-formation and longer diaphragm life. On the laboratory scale, the method leads to good results; but, the use of alcohol on the technical scale has many disadvantages, the chief of which are loss of solvent by evaporation, high cell resistances, dilution of alcohol by flow of water from the anolyte, and last but not the least, the hazard of fire. Elbs (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 209) suggested the reduction of nitro compounds without a solvent, the depolariser, *i.e.*, the nitro compound in this case, being maintained in a state of emulsion by stirring. Based on this idea, no fewer than 12 different patents have been taken out during the years 1900 to 1917. In some of these (Loeb, D. R. P. 116467 of 1900) the reduction is carried out in alkaline emulsion upto the azoxy-stage, the solution then acidified and reduction continued, leading to the production of benzidine in the electrolytic cell itself. In others (Meister, Lucius and Brunning, D. R. P. 127727 of 1900), the reduction is carried out on similar lines, but the diaphragm is dispensed with by the use of a small anode of iron. Sometimes again (Gesellschaft für chemische Industrie, D. R. P. 297019 of 1917), a diaphragm is dispensed with by conducting the reduction in a solvent like benzene, the cathode being set at the interface of the two layers and rotated at such a speed that neither a too fine nor too gross an emulsion is formed.

The methods outlined in these procedures involve either the use of a non-electrolytic solvent like alcohol or benzene, or the use of the depolariser in a state of emulsion by stirring. Later, it was found that concentrated solutions of salts of certain aromatic acids had good solvent properties and McKee and Gerapostolou (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1935, 68, 329) found that concentrated solutions of mixtures of sodium and potassium xylene sulphonates were excellent solvents for nitro compounds, and particularly suitable for employment as solvents in electro-reduction.

Our main objective in undertaking this work was to find out which of the several promising methods was suitable for large-scale reduction and the optimum conditions for operating the selected method.

(1) *Reduction in alcoholic solution.*—Experiments using 350 g. of the nitro compound were carried out. It was found that in order to prevent the azo and hydrazo compounds from being thrown out of solution due to the progressive dilution of the alcohol, it was necessary to add at intervals further quantities of alcohol. It also became obvious that the reduction demanded operation at uneconomical voltages. The method, therefore, was considered unsuitable for operating on the industrial scale.

(2) *Reduction in a saturated solution of sodium and potassium xylene sulphonates.*—In our attempts to reproduce the results of McKee and Gerapostolou, several defects were noticed in the operation of the method. These were (a) excessive diffusion of the catholyte into the anolyte even with dense alundum diaphragms, the sulphuric acid getting extremely dark and viscous, which increased the cell resistance, (b) deterioration of the xylene sulphonate solution both in conductivity and in solvent power by repeated use, (c) the large admixture (up to 20%) of azobenzene with the hydrazobenzene produced, even though a large excess of current had been passed, and the reduction conducted at as low a current density as 1 amp. sq. dm., (d) fairly high cell voltage: in a cell handling 4.5 litres of xylene sulphonate solution and 1 kg. of nitro compound and with dense alundum diaphragms, 8 volts were found necessary for passing 40 amps. on an effective cathode surface of 40 sq. dm. On the whole the view expressed by McKee and others on the great utility of this method for the large-scale production of hydrazo compounds could not be confirmed. It was found suitable for the production of azo compounds in good yields, but not of hydrazo compounds.

(3) *Reduction in alkaline emulsion.*—All the recorded information on the subject is in the form of patent specifications. A systematic study of the reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline emulsion was therefore undertaken, the preliminary experiments being conducted at monel, lead and iron cathodes, the anolyte in all cases being a 30% solution of sodium hydroxide kept inside a porous cylinder. As a result of these experiments it was found that (i) nitrobenzene is reduced at a monel cathode to a mixture of hydrazo- and azobenzene, (ii) the addition of lead oxide carried the reduction to completion, less than 5% of azo compound being found in the end product, (iii) at a lead cathode more than 90% of hydrazobenzene and 4 to 5% of azobenzene were obtained—the addition of lead oxide was found unnecessary, but the cathode was corroded by the action of alkali to some extent and the dissolved lead redeposited in a loose form, (iv) at an iron cathode in the presence of lead oxide the yield of hydrazobenzene was the highest, about 93%, and the azobenzene was the lowest, about 3%, (v) the current efficiency of the processes was good, only 10 to 20% of excess current having to be passed over that required theoretically, (vi) the formation of a crust of hydrazobenzene which was deposited on the cathode and the diaphragm, was a drawback in the earlier experiments, but this was removed later by the addition of xylene at a suitable stage, which helped in the removal of hydrazobenzene and in carrying the reduction to completion.

These preliminary experiments showed that the reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline emulsion was superior to the other methods, both from the point of view of ease of operation and yield and quality of the hydrazobenzene. A systematic study of the reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline emulsion was next undertaken with special

reference to the following factors: influence of current density, concentration of alkali and of depolariser and of addition agents. Iron was selected as the most suitable cathode from the point of view of technical application on a large scale. A cell of a simple design was made in which the parts could be easily assembled and in which all the factors except the variable factor under study could be reproduced to the minutest detail. The description of the cell, as designed for the purpose, has been given fully in *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* (1946, pp. 564-565). This cell has been of great value in conducting related studies with other nitro compounds like *ortho*-nitrotoluene *ortho*-nitroanisole, etc.

A typical reduction was conducted as follows. The alkali of the specified strength was heated to boiling with the addition agent so as to dissolve the latter and introduced into the cell. The porous diaphragm was also filled up to the same level with 30% alkali. The current was passed at 20 amps. for about 15 minutes with heating, and when the temperature had reached 80°, the nitro compound was added. The reduction was carried out at the specified amperage, keeping the temperature at 80°. When 90% of the theoretical current had been passed, 200 c.c. of xylene were added and the reduction continued till the solvent layer was just colourless. In some cases where the colour was not completely discharged, the reduction was carried on till the solvent layer had a constant shade of colour. The alkali and xylene layers were withdrawn from the cell, separated, and any free alkali in the xylene layer neutralised by passing carbon dioxide. The xylene layer was then poured into acid for benzidine transformation. When 100 g. of nitrobenzene had been taken, the transformation was effected by pouring into 80 c.c. of HCl (*d* 1.16) and 150 g. of ice, stirring for 5 hours in the cold and raising the temperature during the sixth hour to gentle boiling. The pasty mass was then filtered and the residue washed with xylene to free it from azobenzene. The filtrate consisted of two layers, the aqueous layer containing benzidine hydrochloride and the xylene layer, azobenzene. The residue consisting of benzidine hydrochloride was converted into the insoluble sulphate by addition of the calculated amount of dilute sulphuric acid. The benzidine sulphate was filtered, dried and weighed. The acid filtrate from this was basified, steam-distilled to remove aniline, and the aniline estimated by the bromide-bromate method. The azobenzene was recovered from the xylene layer by blowing in steam and removing the xylene.

In interpreting the results, some important points must be borne in mind :

(i) *Influence of current density.*—Since satisfactory yields of hydrazobenzene were obtained only by the addition of lead oxide, all the experiments on the influence of current density were conducted only after the addition of this compound. The lead oxide was first dissolved in the catholyte forming sodium plumbite. On passing the current, lead was deposited on the cathode in a spongy state. Since it was not possible to compute the exact surface offered by the spongy lead, only the surface offered by the cathode was taken into account. In any case, it can be assumed that the surface offered by the spongy lead will be a constant factor in all the experiments, provided that the same amount of lead oxide had been added.

(ii) *Influence of concentration of alkali.*—Current efficiency is not appreciably affected by increasing the alkali strength. There is a definite improvement in the material yield.

(iii) *Influence of concentration of depolariser.*—There is no marked improvement in current efficiency by increase of depolariser concentration. Material yield, is, however, definitely improved by increase of depolariser concentration. On the technical scale the increased cell voltage due to increase of depolariser concentration may be a disadvantage.

(iv) *Influence of added compounds.*—Lead oxide is the most valuable addition agent. At the end of the reduction, lead is completely absent in the alkali layer. In technical operation, after completion of one reduction and withdrawal of the charge, a fresh charge can be added and the reduction continued without addition of any fresh amount of lead oxide, since the spongy lead from the previous reduction is almost completely retained in the cathode chamber.

The reason for the increased formation of hydrazo compound by the addition of lead oxide seems to be due to increased overvoltage when the metal is deposited on the cathode. In addition, because of the large surface area offered by the lead sponge, more intimate contact between the cathode and depolariser is favoured, so that rapid reduction can occur.

From the experimental data presented above, it has been proved that electrolytic reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline emulsion at an iron cathode is probably superior to all other methods for the production of benzidine and is very suited for adoption on the industrial scale. The yield of benzidine obtained is nearly 90% of the theoretical and is about equal to that obtained by Fierz David ("Fundamental Operations of Dye Chemistry", 1927, p. 60) by chemical methods or that obtained in reduction with sodium amalgam or that claimed for the electrolytic method stated to be in operation in Switzerland (Fichter, Congress International of Electricity, Paris, Section I, Rapport No. 19, 1932, p. 6).

A study of the process on a pilot-plant scale was undertaken to study fully the economic aspects of the process. At first the reductions were conducted in a cell handling 2 kg. of nitrobenzene, with a cathode surface for 40 sq. dm. and operated at 100 amps. and then in a cell handling 10 kg. with cathode surface of 200 sq. dm. and operated at 450 amps.

As in the small-scale experiments described previously, the vessel of sheet iron itself served as the cathode chamber. Due to the difficulty of getting iron gauze, additional cathode surface was provided by a set of sheet iron vanes. An oval vessel was preferred to ensure a more uniform distribution of current. Instead of using a single anode set in a large central cylindrical diaphragm, three anodes in three smaller cylindrical diaphragms, arranged along the longer axis of the vessel, were employed. This was helpful in distributing the current evenly, avoiding overheating and in lowering the bath voltage.

The hydrazobenzene formed in the reduction was removed by xylene as in small-scale experiments and the large cell was operated with the same ease and smoothness as the small cell. No undesirable heating effects were noticed even with the large current and the cell was maintained at 80° quite easily by regulating the flow of water in the jacket. The only attention needed was to withdraw the weakened anolyte

at intervals of about six hours, fortify it to 20 to 25% and return it to the anode chambers, a process requiring only a few minutes each time. In an industrial cell, this operation may quite easily be made automatic by the regulated addition of solid caustic soda, so that there need be no interruption during the reduction. In an industrial electro-organic reduction, the unit cells are rarely operated at more than 1,000 amps., and large amounts are handled by multiplying such units, each carrying not more than 1,000 amps. and increasing the duration of reduction as required. Our pilot plant, operated at 450 amps., can therefore furnish a fairly accurate idea of the operational features of the industrial cell. It is seen that the results obtained in the small-scale experiments are reproducible on the pilot-plant scale, both with regard to current and material yields. The process of electro-reduction of nitrobenzene in alkaline emulsion can therefore be considered technically sound and suitable for adoption on the industrial scale.

2. *o*-Nitrotoluene

References to the electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene are contained in patent specifications (cf. Brunner, E.P. 15750, 1915).

In the electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene, our studies were restricted to reduction at an iron cathode.

The most disturbing feature in all the reductions is the large proportion of toluidine which is simultaneously formed with the hydrazotoluene (cf. Diffenbach, D.R.P. 197714, Friedländer, 9, 112). It appears difficult to suppress amine formation to any appreciable extent. However, according to Löb (*Z. Elektrochem*, 1904, 10, 582), by proper adjustment of the cathode potential any desired product can be formed. The cathode potential should be held at such a level that reduction does not proceed beyond the phenylhydroxylamine stage. When all the phenylhydroxylamine derivative is used up in forming the azoxy compound by condensation with the nitroso compound, the cathode potential can be raised to a level where reduction of azoxy to hydrazo compound can take place. It is difficult to say how far this is practicable on a technical scale. Amines like toluidine or anisidine, are, however, not without value and their simultaneous formation along with hydrazo compounds need not render the electrolytic method for the production of the diamines unsound technically.

In a standard reduction, a little over 56 g. of hydrazotoluene was formed for every 100 g. of *o*-nitrotoluene reduced. With an 85% yield in the conversion, this ought to give nearly 70 g. of toluidine sulphate, but only 53 g. of toluidine sulphate were obtained.

3. *o*-Nitroanisole

The electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitroanisole in alkaline emulsion has not so far been reported. The reduction was therefore studied with reference to the following factors: influence of catalysts, current density, concentration of alkali and of depolariser. From the results obtained the following conclusions were drawn:

(1) At an iron cathode the reduction does not proceed to an appreciable extent beyond the azoxyanisole stage and anisidine is formed in large amounts as a by-product.

(2) The most satisfactory catalyst is lead monoxide leading to the highest yield of hydrazoanisole.

(3) Zinc oxide leads to more of anisidine being formed and a marked inhibition of reduction to the hydrazo stage.

(4) The addition of tin oxide takes the reduction to completion and there was hardly any azo or azoxy bodies in the reduction products but anisidine preponderates over the hydrazo body as in the previous cases.

(5) Ceric sulphate or vanadium pentoxide are of no value in increasing the yield of hydrazoanisole. In the presence of these compounds, the main products are anisidine and a mixture of azo- and azoxyanisole, hydrazo formation being negligible.

Since lead oxide was indispensable for the production of the hydrazo compound in good yields, the studies relating to influence of the rest of the factors were conducted only with the addition of this agent. The following conclusions were drawn from the results:—

(1) There is no appreciable diminution in anisidine formation by operating at a lower current density.

(2) There is no definite improvement in the yield of hydrazoanisole by increasing the concentration of alkali above 10%.

(3) By operating with a depolariser concentration of one to four volumes of alkali, the dianisidine is obtained in the highest yield; nearly 80% of theoretical. As in the case of the reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene, it does not seem possible to reduce the formation of amine to any considerable extent by the alteration of conditions. Since anisidine is also of value as a dye-intermediate, its production simultaneously with hydrazoanisole need not be considered as an objection to the application of the electrolytic method on a large scale.

The standard method of procedure for the reduction and isolation of products has been used. Yield of hydrazoanisole (m.p. 102°) was 72.1% of theory, and *o*-anisidine, 22% of theory. Yield of Dianisidine or 3:3'-dimethoxybenzidine (m.p. 135°) on conversion of hydrazoanisole was 90%.

4. *o*-Nitrochlorobenzene

The reduction of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene was conducted on the basis of results obtained from earlier studies, employing lead monoxide as addition agent, a depolariser concentration of one to four volumes of sodium hydroxide and a low current density, such as 1 amp./sq. dm. It was seen that the preparation of *o*-dichlorohydrazobenzene in nearly 85% yield was possible by employing the above conditions, the current efficiency also reaching a high value. The hydrazo compound is obtained in a state of high purity, melting sharply at 87°, and is almost colourless

The most noteworthy feature about *o*-dichlorohydrazobenzene is its extraordinary

stability in air and resistance to the "benzidine change" as compared to hydrazo-toluene or hydrazoanisole. It was only after employing 10 mols. of 50% sulphuric acid, that the "benzidine change" could be effected in a yield of 91.5% of the dichlorobenzidine.

Ortho- or 3:3'-dichlorobenzidine can therefore be prepared in an overall yield of more than 80% by the electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene in alkaline emulsion.

5. 2:5-Dichloro-1-nitrobenzene

The study of this reduction was also restricted mainly to a few specific conditions. It was found that other conditions being equal, increase in the strength of the alkali employed caused an increase in the yield and in the current efficiency. This is probably due to better emulsification obtaining with alkali of strength approximating to that of the nitro compound. The best improvements in yields as well as the current efficiency are realised by operating with lower current density of 1 amp./sq.dm. and with a depolariser concentration of one volume to four volumes of catholyte. These would appear to be the optimum conditions for the preparation of tetrachlorobenzidine.

2:2':5:5'-Tetrachlorohydrazobenzene is a light yellow solid (m.p. 123.5°). Its stability in air and resistance to the benzidine transformation are even more marked than that of 2:2'-dichlorohydrazobenzene. Prolonged boiling with a larger excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid has to be carried out before it can be completely converted into the benzidine. Tetrachlorobenzidine has been prepared in this way, in a yield of nearly 85% as a grey powder, which crystallises from alcohol in orange-yellow flakes melting at 137.5°. It is a very feeble base and its salts, like the hydrochloride or sulphate, are immediately hydrolysed to the free base by the addition of water. The diacetyl derivative, crystallised from acetic acid, forms colourless needles (m.p. 297°) and the dibenzoyl derivative also crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (m.p. 250-52°). 3:3':6:6'-Tetrachlorobenzidine has been obtained also by purely synthetic means as described by Dey *et al.* to confirm the identity of the electrolytic product.

6. 2-Nitro-4-chloroanisole

There is no reference in literature to the electrolytic reduction of 2-nitro-4-chloroanisole in alkaline medium.

Since the melting point of 2-nitro-4-chloroanisole was 98-99°, and the reduction was carried out generally at 80°, the nitro compound had to be kept in solution in 100 c.c. of benzene in the electrolytic cell. The following conclusions were drawn from a set of experiments conducted in order to arrive at the most favourable condition for the formation of the dichlorohydrazoanisole :

(1) Lead oxide is an indispensable catalyst for the production of dichlorohydrazoanisole.

(2) The formation of chloroanisidine in appreciable amounts (12 to 20%) is unavoidable.

(3) An increase in the concentration of the alkali (from 10 to 30%) results in increase in the yield of amine and a consequent decrease in the yield of the hydrazo compound.

(4) A current density of 1 amp./sq. dm. and a concentration of 10% sodium hydroxide while employing an increase depolariser concentration of 120 g. in 387 c.c. of the alkali gives the best yield of the hydrazo compound and reduces the amine formation to a minimum.

Dichlorohydrazoanisole (71.7% yield) is a light yellow solid (m.p. 116°) which turns deep orange when exposed to air, probably due to oxidation to azo compound. When treated with acids it undergoes the "benzidine transformation" readily to give 3:3'-dimethoxy-6:6'-dichlorobenzidine (m.p. 170-71°). 4-Chloro-*o*-anisidine (m.p. 80-81°) occurs as a side product to an extent of 16.2%.

7. 2-Nitro-4-chlorophenetole

Neither electrolytic nor chemical reduction of this nitro compound to its hydrazo derivative has been reported so far in literature. Conditions similar to those worked out in the case of the preparation of allied compounds were applied in the present instance, but the yield of the hydrazo compound was relatively poor and the product was invariably contaminated with appreciable quantities of the corresponding azo and azoxy derivatives. Apart from the chlorophenetidine that is simultaneously produced, there is evidence also for the formation of other by-products, one of which appears to be a phenol. In this reduction also, a solvent had to be used. Instead of benzene, xylene was employed owing to its better solvent action on the products.

The crude dichlorohydrazophenetole obtained in a yield of 70 to 72% is an orange-yellow solid which turns deep orange on exposure to air, probably due to oxidation to azo compound. On crystallisation from xylene, it separates as bright yellow needles (m.p. 152°). In regard to the "benzidine transformation" of the hydrazo compound, despite several attempts at variations of the general method of boiling with mineral acids, the conversion did not exceed 64% of theory and to effect this, both concentrated hydrochloric acid and dilute sulphuric acid were found to behave equally well.

B. REDUCTION OF AROMATIC NITRO COMPOUNDS IN ACID MEDIA

The cathodic reduction of aromatic nitro compounds in acid media leads to a variety of products, the course of the reduction being to a large extent conditioned by the strength of the catholyte, the influence of the electrode material and the presence or absence of addition agents in the electrolyte. In dilute acid solution or suspension, according to Haber (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1898, 4, 506), a nitro compound reduced at cathodes having a low overvoltage, such as platinum, yields a mixture of amine, aminophenol, azoxybenzene, azobenzene and benzidine. At high overvoltage

cathodes like those of lead, tin, mercury and zinc, although the reduction leads mainly to the production of amines, the presence of addition agents is said (D.R.P. 295841, 1915) to give good yields of aminophenols too. The aminophenols, however, occur in larger yields when the reduction takes place at a low overvoltage cathode in strongly acid media (Gattermann *et al.*, *Ber.* 1893, 26, 1844; 1894, 27, 1927; 1896, 29, 3024). The bulk of the previous work in this field had related to the electrolytic preparation of amines, with perhaps the sole exception of the case of nitrobenzene, where conditions for the reduction to *para*-aminophenol had been studied by several workers (Noyes and Clement, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 990; Caeser, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1927, 52, 95). A systematic study was therefore undertaken on the electrolytic reduction of a series of aromatic nitro compounds, keeping in view our object of getting the maximum yield of the aminophenol and a minimum of the amine. Nitrobenzene was the first compound to be investigated and it was later followed by studies on the reduction of *ortho*- and *meta*-nitrotoluene, *m*-dinitrobenzene, *m*-nitroaniline, *o*-nitrochlorobenzene and *o*-nitrophenetole on the same lines; the results obtained have been the subject of several publications (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1946, 5, 574; 1947, 6, 83; 1948, 7, 107, 113 etc.). Apart from developing suitable methods for the production of aminophenolic compounds, these investigations have resulted in certain observations of general interest. They have made it clear for example, that the overvoltage effect, varying from electrode to electrode, is by no means the only factor which controls the course of these reductions. There is also the catalytic influence of the cathode material, as distinct from its overvoltage effect, which has not so far been studied with a view to apportioning the relative influence of each of these on the course of the reactions.

Gattermann (*loc. cit.*, *Ber.*, 1893, etc.) was the first to describe the electrolytic preparation of aminophenolic compounds by the reduction of aromatic nitro compounds in acid media; he used warm concentrated sulphuric acid as the catholyte and platinum as electrode metal. Since Gattermann's classical experiments, several modifications have been reported by way of patent specifications (Darmstadter, D.R.P. 150809, 1901, etc.) and other literature, specially in regard to the electrolytic preparation of *p*-aminophenol. In fact, during the war of 1914 to 1918, several tons of *p*-aminophenol were manufactured by Thatcher's modification of the Gattermann procedure, substituting carbon electrodes for the platinum, and also by Eastman Kodak by another modification of the same procedure (See McDaniel, Schneider and Ballard, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1921, 39, 441).

Most of these improvements as well as those that followed later (e.g. those of Darmstadter, Burwell, Shoji, Brigham and Lukens, Altpeter and Khirkhgof) were aimed to lessen the rigour of the operating conditions in the Gattermann procedure by the use of less concentrated sulphuric acid and also replacement of the expensive cathode by less costly material. The mechanism of the formation of *p*-aminophenol by the electro-reduction of nitrobenzene is well understood. The β -phenylhydroxylamine molecule, formed initially by the reduction of nitrobenzene, rearranges itself in the presence of strong acid to *p*-aminophenol. The β -phenylhydroxylamine is also a good depolariser and can be further reduced to aniline at the cathode. The relative amounts of aniline and *para*-aminophenol will therefore depend on the relative speed

of rearrangement of the phenylhydroxylamine molecule and of its reduction to aniline. If therefore the reduction of phenylhydroxylamine to aniline could be retarded, higher yields of *para*-aminophenol might be expected. It has been suggested that this could be achieved by the addition of anti-catalysts or by the use of alloy electrodes.

The most rational approach for evolving a technical method appears to be on the lines suggested by Imray (E.P. 18081, 1915) by the use of anti-catalysts, and it is therefore surprising that no work has been carried out on the basis of these ideas. In almost all the reductions studied, maximum aminophenolic formation takes place in a catholyte of 20 to 30% sulphuric acid in the presence of suitable addition agents. In the case of *m*-dinitrobenzene and *m*-nitroaniline, however, although somewhat satisfactory yields were obtained at these dilutions, better yields resulted when a 40% sulphuric acid solution was employed as catholyte. The cathode material for these reductions consisted of lead, copper, monel or nickel at all of which under the conditions of the experiment, both aminophenols and amines were produced. Amongst these, copper and monel were found to be the most suitable cathode materials.

Mercury being a metal of high overvoltage, should, according to the accepted principles, have not only facilitated the reduction of the nitro compound to the hydroxylamine but also carried it further to the amino stage, giving little time for the hydroxylamine derivative to undergo isomerisation or enter into side-reactions. The experimental evidence seems, however, to show that the contrary is the case. Instead of reducing the hydroxylamine further to the amine stage, the mercury definitely helps in accelerating the speed of isomerisation to the aminophenolic compound, even in a comparatively dilute acid medium. This peculiar role of mercury is played by copper also in the status of cathode material, since reductions in the presence of its salt or otherwise have, in many cases, led to an increased yield of the aminophenol.

When mercuric sulphate is added to the catholyte and the reduction conducted in the usual manner, the cathode (copper or monel) is deposited with a shining surface of mercury. It was therefore considered to be of interest to examine if these results could be reproduced by using cathodes pre-coated with a mercury surface without further addition of mercuric sulphate. In the case of nitrobenzene pre-amalgamation of the cathode was observed to have the same effect as addition of mercuric sulphate, while in the cases of *o*- and *m*-nitrotoluenes and of *m*-nitroaniline, pre-amalgamation led to even greater reduction and to better yields of the aminophenols than when mercuric sulphate was used along with an unamalgamated cathode.

Another interesting fact that was observed in the course of studies of these reductions was the effect of copper sulphate added to the catholyte. The finely divided copper seems to play, as already indicated, the same role as that of mercury, and when copper sulphate was used in conjunction with amalgamated cathodes, relatively good yields of aminophenols and small yields of amines resulted. As regards the extent of reduction, in most cases, substantial improvements could be noticed. These results do not permit any definite conclusions being drawn as to which of the two, mercury or copper, acts as a better catalyst, in speeding up the isomerisation of the hydroxylamino derivative.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

For all the reductions, the current was supplied from a dynamo with an output of 100 amps. at 6 volts. The anodes were in all cases made of lead and consisted of cylinders 1" in diameter and 2" in height. The anolyte was sulphuric acid of the same strength as the catholyte. It was found necessary to change the anolyte during the experiment, in certain cases, where the voltage rose to above 7 volts, but generally in all the reductions, the voltage was maintained between 4 and 7 volts. The materials of the cathodes experimented with were those of copper, monel, nickel and lead. The diaphragms used were those of German biscuit porcelain specially resistant to acids, 5" high and 2.5" in diameter. The working up of the products in the case of the reduction of nitrobenzene, *o*- and *m*-nitrotoluene, *o*-nitrochlorobenzene and *o*-nitrophenetole was as follows. At the end of the reduction, the acid solution is steam distilled to remove the nitro compound remaining unreduced and then filtered to remove insoluble matter through a glass sintered funnel. The acid solution is then neutralised carefully with a strong solution of soda ash till the solution just turns red litmus blue. Sufficient acid is then added to make the solution just turn blue litmus red. A few c. c. of a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite are then added and about 50-100 g. of decolourising charcoal. The mixture is then steam-distilled to remove the amine. *It is absolutely necessary at this stage that the mixture should not be even slightly on the alkaline side. The purity of the product obtained depends entirely on this.* The distillate is worked up for the amine. The hot solution is filtered from the charcoal and the pale yellow filtrate left overnight, preferably in the refrigerator, where the major portion of the aminophenolic body crystallises out and is filtered and dried. The mother-liquor is concentrated *in vacuo* in a stream of hydrogen, the concentration being stopped at the point when inorganic materials start separating. The solution is cooled, filtered and the residue washed with a small amount of water containing sodium bisulphite. The aminophenolic compound thus obtained is dried and added to the main portion.

The product of reduction of *m*-nitroaniline and 2:4-dinitrophenol being, in each case, 2:4-diaminophenol, its mode of isolation is different from that of the mono-amino-phenols. In these reductions therefore after the electrolysis, the acid solution is cooled and filtered to remove unreduced nitro compounds (in the cases of *m*-dinitrobenzene and 2:4-dinitrophenol) and the clear solution concentrated under reduced pressure in an atmosphere of hydrogen. As soon as solid begins to separate the concentration is stopped and the contents cooled and filtered on a glass sintered crucible, the solid being pressed to remove as much of the sulphuric acid as possible. The sulphate thus obtained is dissolved in a little boiling water, the filtered solution poured into 10 times its volume of absolute alcohol, cooled and kept in the frigidaire. The precipitated sulphate is filtered off and the alcohol recovered from the filtrate. The sulphate is finally dried over sulphuric acid in an evacuated desiccator and weighed. In order to determine the purity of the diaminophenol sulphate, the nearly insoluble oxalate is prepared from each sample of the sulphate and the yields of diaminophenol formed calculated, based on these values.

The precipitation of diaminophenol oxalate from the sulphate is conducted as follows:—5 g. of the sulphate are dissolved by warming in 15 c.c. of water, and a solution of 5 g. of potassium oxalate in 25 c.c. of hot water added, the temperature of the mixed solution being about 40°. White crystals of diaminophenol oxalate begin to separate almost immediately. They are filtered after cooling in the frigidaire, washed with a small quantity of cold water and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The more important of the observations made and the results obtained during this investigation are given below.

1. *Nitrobenzene* (See Dey, Govindachari and Rajagopalan, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1946, 5A, pp. 574-81).—In the small-scale experiments, conducted mostly in the nature of preliminary investigations, using 100 g. of nitrobenzene at a time, the most satisfactory results were obtained with copper or monel cathodes in the presence of mercury. Experiments were then conducted on a larger scale with the cathode combinations which proved satisfactory in the small-scale experiment and using 1,000 to 1,500 g. of nitrobenzene at copper or monel cathode and lead anode with a catholyte consisting of sulphuric acid of density 1.2 and containing 0.5 to 1.0% of mercury or cerium salt on the weight of nitrobenzene taken. The process is superior in simplicity of operation, high yield and purity of product and low upkeep charges, to the many other methods cited earlier in this paper, and would therefore be most suitable for adoption on a technical scale. Moreover, the nitrobenzene is reduced in a state of emulsion in dilute sulphuric acid containing acid only a little more than what is required for neutralisation of the product formed. The cathode and anode are of metals which are low in cost and of which plentiful supplies can be had. The corrosion of the electrodes is negligible. The cell voltage is reasonably low and the yield per kw.hr. is nearly 90 g., nearly double that obtained in Gattermann or modified Gattermann procedures. The *p*-aminophenol was of high purity, was almost colourless and melted sharply at 183°.

2. *o*-Nitrotoluene (Dey, Maller and Pai, *ibid.*, 1948, 7B (8), 107-113).

The electro-reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene in acid emulsion can give rise mainly to two products, viz., *o*-toluidine and 4-amino-*m*-cresol. As a result of this investigation, the highest yield of the aminocresol (46% of theory) was obtained when an amalgamated monel cathode was employed in the presence of copper sulphate as catalyst (5-10 g.). The best acid concentration was 30% and so far as the extent of reduction is concerned, although perhaps not so far as the material yields go, lower concentrations serve equally well, e.g., 20%.

3. *m*-Nitrotoluene (Dey, Maller and Pai, *loc. cit.*, pp. 113-115).—*m*-Nitrotoluene was treated under the same conditions as those found best for the reduction of its *ortho*-isomer, viz., catholyte: 100 g. in 400 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid; anolyte: 50 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid; cathode: amalgamated monel; anode: lead; temperature:

70-75°; current density: 3.9 amps./sq.dm.; current strength: 20 amps./ hr.; total current passed (theoretical): 80 amp.hrs.; 88.8% of the nitro compound were reduced, yielding 55.2% (by theory) of 4-amino-*o*-cresol and 15.9% (by theory) of *m*-toluidine.

4. *o*-Nitrochlorobenzene.—The best conditions worked out and results obtained so far in connection with the acid electrolysis of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene are given below:

Conditions:—Cathode: copper; catholyte: 100 g. of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene in 100 c. c. of xylene and 400 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid; anode: lead; anolyte: 50 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid; catalyst: 10 g. of copper sulphate; temperature: 50-55°; current strength: 20 amps./hr; current density: 5.99 amps./sq.dm.; total current passed: 84 amp. hrs. (theoretical).

Results:—Current efficiency 54%; *o*-chloroaniline: 24% of theory; *m*-chloro-*p*-aminophenol: 29.1% of theory.

5. *o*-Nitrophenetole.—The reduction of *o*-nitrophenetole to 6-aminoresorcinol-monoethyl ether (6-amino-3-hydroxy-1-ethoxybenzene, m.p. 170°) has been conducted under the following conditions: 100 g. of *o*-nitrophenetole (b.p. 187-189° at 20 to 22 mm.) in a catholyte of 400 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid; anolyte: 50 c.c. of the same acid; catalyst: copper sulphate, 10 g.; cathode: monel; anode: lead; temperature: 80-85°; current strength: 20 amps./hr. and total current passed (theoretical): 64.2 amp. hrs.; current density: 3.9 amps./ sq.dm.

Results:—Current efficiency: 75.3%; yield of 6-aminoresorcinol-monoethyl ether: 34.7%; yield of *o*-phenetidine: 19.4%

Note: 6-Aminoresorcinol-monoethyl ether has not been described in literature.

6. *m*-Dinitrobenzene (Dey and Udupa, *ibid.*, 1947, 6B, 83-90).—The reduction of *m*-dinitrobenzene kept in a state of emulsion in dilute sulphuric acid was conducted systematically. As a result of this study the following points have come to light:

(1) At copper and monel cathodes, 2:4-diaminophenol can be obtained in nearly 35 to 45% yield by employing sulphuric acid of 40% strength, and using mercuric

sulphate and ceric sulphate in combination as catalysts. Lower strengths of acid do not favour the formation of the diaminophenol, and the use of any strength higher than 50% not only does not improve the yields but also at the same time leads to corrosion of the cathodes and anodes.

(2) In order to obtain the best yield of the diaminophenol the ratio of depolariser to acid should be maintained at 1: 5.3.

(3) A current density of 7.69 amps./sq.dm. in the case of copper and 4.55 amps. sq.dm. in the case of monel seems to be the optimum when sulphuric acid of 40% strength is used.

(5) As regards the effect of addition agents, especially of mercuric and ceric sulphates, it was noticed that in the absence of the latter agents, the yield of diaminophenol was very low.

As a result of the above studies, a method has now been fully worked out for the preparation of 2:4-diaminophenol. It has been isolated as either the oxalate or sulphate in a maximum yield of 45%. For the purpose, *m*-dinitrobenzene kept in a state of emulsion by stirring with a solvent in a 40% sulphuric acid catholyte was reduced at a copper or monel cathode in the presence of addition agents like mercuric and ceric sulphates, at a temperature of 90°-95°. The formation of *m*-phenylenediamine in small amounts as a by-product was proved by the preparation and analysis of the dibenzoyl derivative from the mother-liquor left after the sparingly soluble diaminophenol oxalate had been precipitated.

7. *m*-Nitroaniline (Dey, Maller, Pai and Udupa, *ibid.*, 1948, 7B, 53).—The reduction of *m*-nitroaniline in acid medium was conducted systematically on the same lines as in the cases of the reduction studies with *m*-dinitrobenzene. The following conclusions were drawn from the results obtained :

(1) The concentration of sulphuric acid which gives the best yield of 2:4-diaminophenol is 40%.

(2) A current density of 2.4 amps./sq.dm. in the case of monel, 2.0 amps./sq.dm. for copper and 3.85 amps./sq.dm. for nickel cathodes appears to be the optimum with sulphuric acid of 40% strength.

(3) For realising the best yields it is found essential to use about one-third more than the theoretical current necessary for the reduction.

(4) Increase of temperature betters the yield up to 50°, which is found to be the optimum.

(5) Copper sulphate, when copper is used as the cathode, mercuric sulphate for monel and nickel sulphate for nickel cathodes catalyses the reductions and high yields of diaminophenol sulphate are obtained (about 74% of theory).

(6) Monel, copper and nickel serve almost equally well as cathode materials.

(7) From the results of changing the concentration of depolariser, it appears that the ratio of one part by weight of *m*-nitroaniline to 10.5 parts by weight of the sulphuric acid content is the optimum for obtaining the maximum yield of diaminophenol, taking into consideration only the yield of the oxalate which is purer than the sulphate.

8. 2:4-Dinitrophenol (Lüb, *Z. elektrochem.*, 1898, 4, 436).—The experimental details in connection with this reduction are exactly similar to those adopted for *m*-nitroaniline. A yield of 81% of the diaminophenol was obtained at a copper cathode without any addition agent in a 30% sulphuric acid catholyte, kept at 90°. Only the theoretical amount of current (17.5 amps. hrs.) was passed at 20 amps./hr. The best yields of the diaminophenol sulphate are obtained in small-scale experiments with 10 g. of dinitrophenol in 400 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid. It may be mentioned here that the yields of diaminophenol sulphate decrease when catalysts like mercuric sulphate, copper sulphate, ceric sulphate and copper powder are used.

I commenced this memorial lecture with a recital of my personal reminiscences of Professor Prafulla Chandra Ray's life and I cannot perhaps do better than conclude it with the words of Sir Edward Thorpe which appeared in *Nature* of March, 6, 1919 and which seem to be peculiarly appropriate to-day: "Her (India's) elevation will not come in Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray's time. He will be spent in her service. But the memory of these services will survive".